

MECHANICAL IMPEDANCE ANALYSIS (MIA): A TECHNIQUE FOR
CURE MONITORING AND FABRICATION CONTROL OF
THERMOSETTING RESINS AND COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A dynamic mechanical technique based on the concept of mechanical impedance analysis (MIA) was constructed for real-time cure monitoring of composites. Dynamic properties such as the storage modulus (E') and the loss tangent ($\tan(\delta)$) of the curing composite can be obtained as a function of cure time by measuring the frequency response function (FRF). The FRF was obtained by exciting the curing composite with an electromagnetic shaker (driven by a random-noise signal generator) and measuring the force of excitation and motional response. These signals are converted to the frequency domain by a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithm and then ratioed to obtain the FRF. Information from this dynamic mechanical data was used to locate the onset of gelation in the curing composite. The signals obtained could also be incorporated into a closed-loop feedback control system for composite fabrication.

INTRODUCTION

The ability to measure viscoelastic properties during the cure of a composite is very important. In-situ measurement is required if automated control of the composite fabrication process is ever to be implemented. Chemical analysis devices such as DSC, HPLC and FTIR are generally used for studying cure kinetics and for determining the onset of gelation and vitrification in resins. However, these techniques are not practical for direct observation in autoclave environments during composite fabrication. Other commercial instruments such as Rheometrics, DMA, and DETA which can also be used for curing reaction studies of small samples are also subject to the same limitation¹. For the thermoset matrix composites, the production quality is controlled by the processing parameters such as the time-at-temperature cycle, the autoclave pressure, and the laminate boundary pressure^{1,2}. But, until recently, no direct measurement instrument was available to ensure consistent automated cure cycles. Once the material has been laid up on the tool and placed inside the autoclave or compression molding machine, the operator could no longer observe or analyze the laminate to ensure it is processed properly.

Most processing of composites can be divided into one of two categories: parameter-controlled or property-controlled. Parameter-controlled cure cycling is similar to a "cookbook" type of approach. A given set of curing conditions including the temperature ramp rate, hold temperature, pressure ramp and cool-down rate are followed as closely as possible throughout the cure cycle. This approach does not take into consideration variations that may occur from sample to sample so final part consistency may not be high. Any automated control system of this type will operate by comparing the actual and specified cure parameters (temperature, pressure) and make changes accordingly. Matchup of the measured parameters with the system-specified parameters does not assure optimal cure of the resin. Property-controlled processing, on the other hand, relates the actual material properties of the curing resin to the degree of cure. The feedback control system used would

compare the actual material parameters measured (E' , $\tan \delta$, dielectric permittivity, etc.) to a material database and then alter the curing conditions accordingly. This would consistently produce the best parts. The corresponding improvement in quality control would also bring down costs. Recently Jang, et al. proposed a new technique of applying the mechanical impedance analysis method (MIA) to characterize the phase transformation behavior of polymers¹⁻⁴. Application of the MIA technique is one possible sensor that could be used for property-controlled feedback. The MIA technique could serve as a complementary or an alternative to microdielectrometry, fluorescence, or ultrasonics, some of the other in-situ cure monitoring systems that are currently in use.

The MIA technique basically involves quantitative measurement of the effect of a vibratory force on a structure. Dynamic behavior of a material is sufficiently described by measuring the ratios of motion to force on a structure. The terminology for the ratio of the force to the velocity is given as "mechanical impedance" while the ratio of acceleration to force is termed the "inertance." Both types of data are equally useful as far as obtaining dynamic mechanical data is concerned. Both types of plots are obtained by taking the respective ratios of the motional and excitation signals in the frequency domain. This transformation is conducted by a Fast-Fourier Transform (FFT) spectrum analyzer. The results in the frequency domain are also known as the frequency response functions (FRF).

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental results for this study consist of two main parts. One part consists of dynamic mechanical characterization of a curing composite beam. The other part is an in-situ measurement of composite cure in a compression molding machine. Vibrational monitoring was conducted using a Hewlett-Packard 3565 multi-channel FFT spectrum analyzer. The first cure monitoring test is a quantitative study of the cure behavior of graphite/epoxy samples using a free-free beam geometry. Samples were composed of 20 layers of SP-319 unidirectional graphite pre-preg. The samples were wrapped in aluminum foil and then connected to an electromagnetic shaker via an extension rod. This rod was attached to the center of the pre-preg beam. Figure 1 shows a schematic of a typical cure monitoring setup. Force and acceleration measurements were taken through a combined transducer, known as an impedance head,

Fig. 1 Block diagram of a MIA cure monitoring system.

connected between the shaker and the extension rod. The aluminum foil was used to prevent flashing of the epoxy during heating. Both $\tan(\delta)$ and E' were calculated for a number of isothermal cure temperatures using the derived equation for a

rectangular cross-section beam. The equation for E' is

$$E' = 48 \Pi^2 \rho l^4 f_n^2 / h^2 \lambda_n^4 \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the beam density, l is the length, h is the thickness, and λ_n is a mode constant having the value 4.730, 7.853, 10.966...etc. for modes 1, 2, 3,..., respectively². The value f_{rn} is the resonant frequency of vibration of the particular mode in question. During cure, all other parameters will remain constant. The equation shows that the modulus is proportional to the square of the natural frequency. This is true for most vibrating systems and can be quite useful if the geometry is too complicated (as is very often the case) for a closed-form equation solution. $\tan(\delta)$ measurements are made using the half-power point method¹.

The second part of the cure study involves in-situ monitoring of an epoxy curing in a mould. The resin system consisted of Araldite 507/HY956 resin with E-glass fiber reinforcement. The material was cured in a compression molding machine. MIA analysis was conducted through a small bleed hole in the side of the mould. An extension rod was inserted into the hole where dynamic viscosity measurements were conducted with the electromagnetic shaker. Figure 2 shows the model of this particular setup. Mechanical impedance analysis of a moving element immersed in a

Fig. 2 Model of the shear resonant vibration of a rubberlike material.

resin solution can be used to obtain the complex shear modulus of the matrix material. A resonant shear motion will occur at the interface between the rubberlike resin material and the moving rod as random oscillation signals are applied by the shaker. Férry proposed an expression for the mechanical impedance of the moving element⁵:

$$F/V = Z_m = bG''/\omega + i(\omega M - Sm'/\omega - bG'/\omega) \quad (2)$$

where

M : mass of the moving element.

Sm' : elastance of the support for moving element.

b : geometry factor $(= \frac{2\pi l}{\ln q - q^2 - 1}, q=R_2/R_1 \text{ for an annular pumping geometry as Fig. 2})$.

ω : angular frequency of apply force.

G : the complex shear modulus of the resin material ($G = G' + iG''$)

At the resonant frequency, ω_0 , the imaginary term vanishes and the force and velocity are in phase; the response is determined only by G'' , and the impedance spectrum passes through a maximum over a range of frequencies. By measuring the absolute value of peak displacement (X) and peak force (F) at resonance, the loss shear modulus can be estimated as

(3)

This equation could also be rewritten in terms of the peak acceleration. $\tan(\delta)$ can then be obtained by the half-power point method and G' obtained from G'' knowing that $\tan(\delta) = G''/G'$.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A number of FRF's for a curing graphite-epoxy beam are shown in Figure 3. The beam was cured isothermally at 160 C while low amplitude vibration was applied. The FRF's consist of inertance plots (Acc/Force) over a frequency range of 0 to 1600 Hz. The curves are plotted in groups of two in order to save space. At 0 minutes, the

Fig. 3. The inertance spectra of a graphite/epoxy laminate cured at 160°C for different cure times.

epoxy is just beginning to soften. Damping is quite large so no noticeable resonance peak is observed. After just 6 minutes, a peak starts to form due to the initial polymerization. As time progresses, polymerization of the epoxy network continues until final gelation occurs at 90 minutes. It can be seen that the resonant frequency shifted a large amount over the cure (800 Hz). This relates to an approximate 800^2 increase in storage modulus. It can also be seen that as curing proceeds, the widths of the peaks decrease. This increase in peak sharpness corresponds to a decrease in damping ($\tan(\delta)$). As crosslinking becomes more

complete, less relaxation mechanisms are available to dissipate the vibrational energy. Plots of the storage modulus and loss tangent for the graphite/epoxy system are shown in Figure 4 for a number of different cure temperatures. As can be seen

Fig. 4 E' and damping for a number of different isothermal cure temperatures (graphite/epoxy).

the storage modulus starts to increase dramatically over a very short period of time. This is the onset of gelation in the epoxy. In an autoclave or compression molding machine, pressure should be applied just prior to this point. If it is applied too early, then excessive flashing will occur due to low viscosity. If it is applied after gelation, then poor consolidation of the laminate plies will be the result. For the $\tan(\delta)$ plots a similar trend occurs. The damping will decrease dramatically during gelation until crosslinking is complete at which time the curve will level out. It should be noted that these measurements are not absolute due to the presence of the aluminum foil. Further tests showed however, that its stiffness effect is negligible compared to the graphite-epoxy beam.

The effect of isothermal cure temperature can also be studied using the data in Figure 4. As can be seen the fully cured value of the storage modulus increases with increasing cure temperature. The higher mobility at higher temperatures allows more complete reaction in the curing epoxy. Once gelation occurs this mobility is drastically reduced. Autoacceleration due to exothermic heat buildup in the epoxy will also increase the reaction rate. Its effects are greater when the polymerization rate is already high (higher isothermal cure temperature). Another factor that affects the final degree of cure is the onset of vitrification. As the epoxy polymerizes, its glass transition temperature T_g will also increase. Vitrification will occur if this T_g value ever catches up with the isothermal cure temperature. Vitrification usually will occur shortly after gelation begins limiting the final degree of crosslinking as the molecules are frozen in place. If the isothermal cure temperature is kept high enough, vitrification will not be a factor. Finally if the temperature is maintained too low (as in the 120 C in Fig. 4), the epoxy will not fully cure within a reasonable time frame. As can be seen for the 120 C cure, the values for the modulus and $\tan(\delta)$ never do plateau indicating incomplete chemical reaction. It is therefore important to choose the curing conditions wisely. Too low a cure temperature will require very long cure times. Too high a temperature will shorten the required time but will require better heating and also can endanger the part to scorching. The optimum cure temperature will typically somewhere in between. The exact temperature will depend

on the geometry of the part and the tooling being used. Inertance spectra for the Araldite 507/HY956 resin system cured in a compression mould were taken and processed based on the shear resonance equation for a rod in a cylinder (Eqn. 2). This data is shown in Figure 5. The dynamic properties were

Fig. 5 Results of press cure monitoring of Araldite 507/HY956 resin by using the MIA method.

evaluated under the assumption of a negligible elastance value for the support of the moving rod and no movement of the shaker due to small oscillation. It should be noted that this data is different from that of the graphite-epoxy beam. Here the shear modulus properties of just the epoxy flashing through the bleed hole are evaluated. For the graphite beams, the modulus of the entire beam is being determined. Since the properties of the resin are the only ones changing, cure monitoring tests performed through the bleed hole are just as informative.

CONCLUSIONS

Application of the MIA technique provides a direct method for monitoring the cure behavior so that the desired properties of composites can be obtained through the controlled time-temperature-pressure cure profile. This MIA technique offers the advantage that no geometry constraint exists in the test coupon. It turns out to be a non-destructive evaluation method for material property control. Since the data acquisition and reduction are handled very rapidly and accurately, this technique may serve as an effective, real-time sensor for in-situ curing control. The same technique can also be used for determining the dynamic mechanical properties of polymers and composites as a function of time and frequency.

REFERENCES

1. Jang, B.Z., and Zhu, G.H., *J. Appl Poly Sci*, 31 (1986), 2627-2646.
2. Jang, B.Z., Shelby, M.D., Hsieh, H.B., and Lin, T.L., 19th Technical Conference, SAMPE, Crystal City, VA, Oct. 13-15, (1987).
3. Jang, B.Z., Hsieh, H.B., and Shelby, M.D., 14th Conf. on Production Research and Technology, sponsored by SME-NSF, Ann Arbor, MI, Oct. (1987).
4. Jang, B.Z., Hsieh, H.B., and Shelby, M.D., 46th ANTEC, Atlanta, GA, April 18-21, (1988).
5. Ferry, J.D., *Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., (1970) 125-157.